

TOURISM BRAND OF UZBEKISTAN: THE ROLE OF GUIDES AND THEIR PROFESSIONAL TRAINING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVITY

Qalandarova Mubinabonu Fayziddin qizi

Andijan State University. Faculty of Social Economics. Student of group 201 in the field of guide support and translation activity

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15916669>

Annotation: The recent policy of accelerated development of tourism in Uzbekistan, attraction of investments in the industry is aimed at maximum realization of the existing considerable potential and enhancement of the country's tourist image. The new impetus is built, first of all, on the solid foundation created in this area during the years of independence. Indeed, every year the interest in Uzbekistan as a land with an amazing history, bright architecture, unique culture is growing in the tourist world. And this is not accidental. There are over seven thousand monuments of different eras and civilizations on the territory of the republic, most of which are located in the ancient cities of the country, such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Tashkent, Shakhrisabz. They are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. Rich flora and fauna, amazing landscape, contrast of natural zones, diversity of cultural traditions and national cuisine, united in one place, can be found only in a few corners of the planet.

Keywords: operational competence, guide-interpreter, specialized centers for professional development, model and methodology, foreign language, professional activity, international cooperation, international communication, discourse.

Rare natural sites of Uzbekistan allowed the republic to rightfully take a leading position among the countries of Central Asia in ecotourism. The world-famous nature reserves deserve special attention, including the Chatkal State Biosphere Reserve, included in the UNESCO list of the world's largest nature reserves. Within the framework of the concept of ecotourism development in Uzbekistan, a lot of work is being done to revive nature and ensure the stability of the ecological situation of the Aydar-Arnasay lake system, the Ugam-Chatkal recreational and Charvak resort areas. Ecotourism is not only an effective tool for preserving natural and cultural heritage, restoring ecosystems, but also an important element of sustainable development of visited regions and improving the well-being of the local population. Vitamin and geotourism can be attributed to new and relatively young, but promising areas of ecotourism in our country. It should be noted that the State Committee for Tourism Development, together with the Ministry of Health, have developed plans for the development of health tourism. The services of medical institutions can become components of tourism products sold in Uzbekistan, primarily to citizens from neighboring countries. This type of tourism makes it possible to combine rest with treatment not only at the health resorts of the republic, but also at medical centers. Comfortable rest as an important component of any trip is ensured by the infrastructure created in the country, which meets world standards. Over 26 years of sovereign development, an extensive network of hotel facilities has been created in Uzbekistan: more than 600 hotels and similar accommodation facilities with various forms of ownership operate, with a capacity of more than 50 thousand beds. Among the most famous are Lotte Hotels, Radisson Blu, Ramada, Wyndham, Hyatt Regency.

Students are offered a specific practical situation representing a set of erroneous actions of a guide-interpreter. The students' task is to develop a program of actions leading to the resolution of the difficulties that have arisen. The application of the case method is aimed at the formation of communicative and professional-personal competencies (communicative, organizational and gnostic components of the professional activity of a guide-interpreter). The project method is used for a comprehensive check of the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students during the development of the special course program "Excursion around the Samara Region in a Foreign Language" and is the conduct of a self-developed excursion on one of the studied types of excursions in the Samara Region. Thus, professional training of guides-interpreters with the purpose of forming operational competence within the framework of the special course "Excursion around the Samara region in a foreign language" is carried out using the following methods of interactive training: game method, discussion method, "brainstorming" method, project method, case method, research methods. At the same time, it becomes possible to form professionally significant competencies of the guide-interpreter and master his professional functions.

References:

Используемая литература:

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Merkulova, L.P., Troiczka, Yu.V. (2018). The development of professional mobility of translators and interpreters: monograph, Samara: Samara University, 184 p.
2. Rudneva, T.I., Strekalova, N.B. (2018). Educational risks in the innovative context of pedagogical activity: monograph, Sy'zran: Vash Vzglyad, 193 p.
3. Rudneva, T.I., Berishvili, O.N., Vinogradova, G.A. (2017). Strategies of modern higher education, Sy'z-ran: Vash Vzglyad, 234 p.